

Vibrational Characteristics of Undoped and M_2SO_4 ($M = K, NH_4, Li$) Doped Triglycine Sulphate Crystals Studied by Raman Spectroscopy

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Abstract

Single crystals of undoped TGS and M_2SO_4 ($M = K, NH_4, Li$) doped TGS have been grown from aqueous solutions by slow evaporation method at room temperature. The grown crystals were characterized by Raman spectroscopy. Laser Raman spectra were observed by Ocean Optics QE65000 Visolator Raman Spectrophotometer in the Raman shift range of 400 cm^{-1} – 2000 cm^{-1} region. Vibrational characteristics and mode assignments of constituent molecules of SO_4^{2-} , COO^- , $C-C$, $CO_2-CH_2-CH_2$, $NH-NH_3$, NH_3 and CO_2 were observed and assigned in this work. The collected Raman lines were found to be agreed with the FTIR results.

Keywords: Undoped and M_2SO_4 doped TGS crystals, Raman spectroscopy, Vibrational characteristics and mode assignments

Introduction

Triglycine Sulphate, $(NH_2CH_2COOH)_3.H_2SO_4$, crystal is considered as one of the potential materials for its wide range of applications, namely, UV tunable laser, second harmonic generation, and pyroelectric infrared sensors due to its high pyroelectric coefficient, optical transmission, and reasonably low dielectric constant [1 - 3]. It is hydrogen bonded ferroelectric crystal having a typical second-order phase transition at Curie temperature of $49^\circ C$ [4, 5]. TGS has a major disadvantage that it depolarized by thermal, mechanical, and electrical means. In order to overcome this difficulty, several studies have been attempted with different organic and inorganic dopants to achieve effective internal bias to stabilize the domains and desired pyroelectric and ferroelectric properties of TGS crystals [6].

Alkali halides such as NaBr and KBr-doped TGS crystals were grown, and the effects of the dopant have been investigated. Metal ion dopants have been added to modify the properties of TGS crystal [8, 9]. Due to the vast applications of TGS crystal, in this work, single crystals of undoped TGS and M_2SO_4 ($M = K, NH_4, Li$) doped TGS have been grown by slow evaporation method and their molecular vibrations were reported by Raman spectroscopic method.

Experiment

Crystal Growth and Raman Spectroscopic Measurement

Single crystals of undoped Triglycine Sulphate, $(NH_2CH_2COOH)_3.H_2SO_4$, (TGS) and M_2SO_4 ($M = K, NH_4, Li$) doped TGS have been grown by slow evaporation method. The details crystal growth conditions were presented in the previous work.

In all spectroscopic techniques, there is a mechanism by which the incident radiation interacts with the molecular energy levels. Raman Spectroscopy can be used to study the vibrational properties of crystals, powders, polymers and even coloured samples (solutions). Raman Scattering is an inelastic scattering of light from molecules. Raman spectroscopy, the mechanism has its origins in the general phenomenon of light scattering, in which the

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electromagnetic radiation interacts with a pulsating, deformable (polarizable) electron cloud. In the specific case of vibrational Raman scattering, this interaction is modulated by the molecular vibrations [7]. Raman spectra of the as-grown crystals were collected on PC controlled Ocean Optics QE65000 Visolator Laser Raman Spectrometer (Institute of Advanced Energy, Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan) in the Raman shift range of 400 cm^{-1} – 2000 cm^{-1} region.

Results and Discussion

According to vibrational analysis, the SO_4^{2-} in free-state is tetrahedral-pyramidal type T_d symmetry [10]. In ideal case, a free tetrahedral T_d sulphate molecule has four types of fundamental modes of vibrations; namely: (ν_1 -mode) symmetric-stretching, (ν_2 -mode) asymmetric-stretching, (ν_3 -mode) dipole and (ν_4 -mode) polarization. The SO_4^{2-} , however, may be distorted from the ideal T_d symmetry due to the effect of dopant material [11].

Raman spectra of the crystals are shown in Fig. 1(a – d). As shown in figures, four normal vibrations were appeared in all Raman spectra. In all spectra, the Raman line at 978 cm^{-1} indicates the ν_1 -mode (symmetric-stretching) is influence on others three types of vibrations because this it is a very strong Raman active mode. The ν_3 -mode (dipole character) of SO_4^{2-} at room temperature phase is often splitting. In the present work, the Raman lines at about 1045 cm^{-1} and 1113 cm^{-1} or 1043 cm^{-1} and 1115 cm^{-1} assigned as the ν_3 -mode of SO_4^{2-} . The ν_2 -mode and ν_4 -mode are not clearly changed in the undoped and doped crystals. The observed Raman shift and vibrational characteristics are tabulated in Table 1. Raman spectra of the crystals are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1(a) Raman spectrum of undoped TGS crystal

Fig. 1(b) Raman spectrum of K₂SO₄ doped TGS crystal

Fig. 1(c) Raman spectrum of (NH₄)₂SO₄ doped TGS crystal

Fig. 1(d) Raman spectrum of Li_2SO_4 doped TGS crystal

Table. 1 The observed Raman shifts and corresponding vibrational mode assignments of undoped and M_2SO_4 ($\text{M} = \text{K}, \text{NH}_4, \text{Li}$) doped TGS crystals

Raman shift (cm^{-1})				Assignment
TGS	$\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{TGS}$	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{TGS}$	$\text{Li}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{TGS}$	
1683	1685	1687	1683	CO_2 -bending
1616	1618	1615	1617	NH_3 -asymmetric bending
1487	1489	1485	1485	NH -in plane bending + (NH_3) -symmetric bending
1441, 1314	1443, 1312	1443, 1316	1442, 1312	CO_2 -symmetric stretching+ CH_2 -twisting+ CH_2 -bending
1113, 1045	1115, 1045	1115, 1043	1115, 1043	SO_4 -dipole
978	978	978	978	SO_4 -symmetric stretching
888, 868	888, 868	888, 869	888, 869	C—C- stretching
672	672	672	672	COO-scissoring
616	620	616	614	SO_4 -polarization
583	581	583	583	COO-rocking
454	451	451	451	SO_4 -bending

Fig. 2 Raman spectra of undoped and M_2SO_4 ($M = K, NH_4, Li$) doped TGS crystals

Conclusion

Single crystals of undoped Triglycine Sulphate, $(NH_2CH_2COOH)_3 \cdot H_2SO_4$, (TGS) and M_2SO_4 ($M = K, NH_4, Li$) doped TGS have been grown by slow evaporation method. The as-grown crystals were colourless and characterized by Raman spectroscopy. Four normal modes of SO_4^{2-} and vibrational characteristics of organic molecules such as COO^- , $C-C$, $CO_2-CH_2-CH_2$, $NH-NH_3$, NH_3 and CO_2 were observed and assigned in this work. The observed Raman lines were found to be agreed with the wavenumbers of FTIR results of my previous work. The wavenumbers of FTIR spectra of the crystals can be well confirmed, thus, by the Raman shifts of Raman spectra.

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